

Kinetics and mechanism of osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of guanidine hydrochloride by alkaline permanganate

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Abstract : The reaction between permanganate and guanidine hydrochloride in alkaline medium has a stoichiometry of 2 : 1 with first order dependence each on [permanganate] and [osmium(VIII)] and fractional order in [OH⁻], while zero order dependence on [guanidine hydrochloride]. No effect of added products, ionic strength and dielectric constant has been observed. Investigation at different temperatures allowed the determination of the activation parameters with respect to slow step of the proposed mechanism. The observed kinetic data were compared with uncatalysed reaction. Entirely different observation obtained are discussed with respect to kinetic result and activation parameters.

Keywords : Kinetics, osmium(VIII), mechanism, guanidine hydrochloride, oxidation.

Introduction

Potassium permanganate is widely used as an oxidizing agent in synthetic as well as in analytical chemistry and also as a disinfectant. The reactions with permanganate are governed by the pH of the medium. Among six oxidation states of manganese from +2 to +7, permanganate, Mn^{VII} is the most potent oxidation state in acid as well as in alkaline medium.

The manganese chemistry involved in these multistep redox reactions is an important source of information as the manganese intermediates are relatively easy to identify when they have sufficiently long life times and oxidation states of the intermediates permit useful conclusion to possible reaction mechanism including the nature of intermediates.

The oxidation by permanganate ion finds extensive applications in organic synthesis¹⁻⁷ especially since the advent of phase transfer catalysis^{3,4,6}, which permits the use of solvents like methylene chloride and benzene. Kinetic studies are important source of mechanistic information on these reactions, as demonstrated by the results referring to unsaturated acids in both aqueous^{1,3-7} and non-aqueous media⁸.

During the oxidation by permanganate, it is evident that permanganate is reduced to various oxidation states in acidic, alkaline and neutral media. Furthermore, the mechanism by which the multivalent oxidant oxidizes a substrate depends not only on the substrate but also on

the medium⁹ used for the study. In strongly alkaline medium, the stable reduction product^{10,11} of permanganate ion is manganate ion, MnO₄²⁻. No mechanistic information is available to distinguish between a direct one-electron reduction to Mn^{VI} (Scheme 1) and a mechanism, in which a hypomanganate is formed in a two-electron reduction followed by a rapid oxidation of the hypomanganate ion¹² (Scheme 2).

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Guanidine hydrochloride (GH) finds its applications in analytical chemistry, pharmaceuticals and polymer industries.

Osmium(VIII) acts as a catalyst in several redox reactions. Particularly in alkaline solution, the osmium(VIII) catalysis of a number of organic and inorganic reactions in alkaline media have been studied¹³. The mechanism of

the catalysis can be quite complicated due to the formulation of different intermediate complexes, free radicals and different oxidation states of osmium.

The literature survey reveals that there are no reports on mechanistic studies of osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of guanidine hydrochloride by alkaline Mn^{VII}. Thus in order to explore the mechanism of oxidation and to know the active species of osmium(VIII) in strongly alkaline medium the detail kinetic study of the title reaction is undertaken.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry and product analysis : Different sets of reaction mixtures containing different amounts of reactants at constant alkalinity and ionic strength and catalyst were allowed to react for 24 h in an inert atmosphere [MnO₄⁻] > [GH]. After the completion of the reaction, solid KI was added followed by acidification with H₂SO₄ (10%). The remaining permanganate was titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate iodometrically¹⁴. The results of titration showed that one mole of guanidine hydrochloride consumes two moles of permanganate in accordance with the eq. (1). The main reaction products were identified as ammonia¹⁵ (Nessler's reagent), and manganate (MnO₄²⁻). CO₂ was qualitatively detected by bubbling N₂ gas through the acidified reaction mixture and passing the liberated gas through a tube containing lime water¹⁶.

Reaction order : The kinetic runs of osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of guanidine hydrochloride by permanganate in aqueous alkaline medium were followed at different initial concentration of oxidant, substrate, catalyst and alkali in turn keeping all other concentrations constant. The reaction orders were determined from the slopes of log *k*_{obs} versus log concentration plots.

Effect of [permanganate] : The oxidant, [permanganate] was varied in the range of 0.5 × 10⁻⁴ to 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ keeping all other conditions constant. Linearity of plots of log [MnO₄⁻] versus time (Fig. 3) indicates the order with respect to [MnO₄⁻] as unity. This was also confirmed by varying [MnO₄⁻] which did not show any change in pseudo-first order rate constants, *k*_{obs}.

Effect of [guanidine hydrochloride] : The substrate, guanidine hydrochloride, was varied in the concentration range of 0.5 × 10⁻³ to 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ at 27 °C keeping all other [reactants] constant. The order in [GH]

was found to be zero.

Effect of [osmium(VIII)] : The catalyst osmium(VIII) concentration was varied in the range 0.5 × 10⁻⁶ to 5.0 × 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³. The linearity of the plot of log *k*_{obs} versus log [Os^{VIII}] with unit slope shows a reaction order of unity in [Os^{VIII}] under the conditions used for this study.

Effect of [alkali] : The effect of alkali on the reaction was studied at constant [MnO₄⁻], [osmium(VIII)] and [guanidine hydrochloride] keeping constant ionic strength of 2.0 mol dm⁻³ at 27 °C. The rate constant increased with the increase in [OH⁻] and order was found to be less than unity from the slopes of log *k*_{obs} versus log [OH⁻] plots.

Effect of ionic strength : The effect of ionic strength was studied by varying the concentration of NaClO₄ from 0.05 to 0.5 mol dm⁻³ at constant concentration of oxidant, reductant, catalyst and alkali. The rate of reaction remains almost unchanged while increasing the [NaClO₄].

Dielectric constant : The dielectric constant (D) of the reaction medium was studied by varying the *t*-butanol-water (Baker sample) content in the reaction mixture. Earlier the inertness of the *t*-butanol towards the oxidant in the reaction mixture had been confirmed. With the increase of *t*-butanol content from 1 to 10% (v/v), the rate remained almost unchanged.

Effect of initially added products : The initially added products such as manganate, and ammonia were studied by varying concentration of each product to ten times. The results did not show any significant effect on the rate of the reaction.

Test for free radicals : To study the intervention of free radical in the reaction, the reaction mixture, to which a known amount of acrylonitrile scavenger had been added initially, was kept for 24 h in an inert atmosphere. On diluting the reaction mixture with methanol, we get precipitate indicating the presence of free radical intervention in the reaction.

Effect of temperature : The effect of temperature was studied at 27, 32, 37 and 42 °C at constant concentration of permanganate, guanidine hydrochloride, Os^{VIII} and ionic strength by varying [OH⁻]. The rate constants, *k* of the slow step of the mechanism were calculated from the intercepts of plots of [Os^{VIII}]/*k*_{obs} versus 1/[OH⁻]. For different temperatures the data is subjected to least square analysis. From the plot of log *k* versus 1/*T*, the energy of activation corresponding to these constants was evaluated and other activation parameters have calculated.

Mechanism : Permanganate ion is a powerful oxidant in an aqueous alkaline medium. As it exhibits many oxidation states, the stoichiometric results and pH of the reaction media play an important role. Under the prevailing experimental conditions at pH > 12, the reduction product of Mn^{VII} is stable and further reduction of Mn^{VI} might be stopped¹⁰. The Diod Array Rapid Scan Spectrophotometer (DRASS) studies have shown that at pH > 12, the product of Mn^{VII} is Mn^{VI} and no further reduction was observed as reported¹⁰ by Simandi *et al.* However on prolonged standing, the green Mn^{VI} is reduced to Mn^{IV} under our experimental conditions.

The permanganate in alkaline medium exhibits various oxidation states, such as Mn^{VII}, Mn^V and Mn^{VI}. The colour of the solution changes from violet to blue and further to green excluding the accumulation of hypomanganate. The violet colour originates from pink of permanganate and blue from hypomanganate is observed during the course of the reaction. The colour change of KMnO₄ solution from violet Mn^{VII} ion to dark green Mn^{VI} ion through blue Mn^V ion has been observed.

Osmium(VIII) is known to form different complexes with hydroxide in basic media as shown in eqs. (2) and (3) where the equilibrium constant K_1 and K_2 have values of 24 and 6.8 dm³ mol⁻¹ respectively¹⁷.

The absorbance of osmium(VIII) becomes almost constant for [OH⁻] above 1.5 mol dm⁻³, indicating the predominance of one species, presumably [OsO₅(OH)]³⁻. The main osmium(VIII) species is likely to be [OsO₅(OH)]³⁻ and formation by equilibrium (3) is of importance in the reaction and this conclusion is agreement with the earlier work¹⁸.

The reaction between permanganate and guanidine hydrochloride in alkaline medium has a stoichiometry of 2 : 1 with first order dependence each on [permanganate] and [osmium(VIII)] and fractional order in [OH⁻], while a zero order dependence on [guanidine hydrochloride]. No effect of added products, ionic strength dielectric constant has been observed. The observed kinetics and other results may be explained by the following mechanism (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

The probable structure of the complex (c) is

The above mechanism envisages a complex formation between oxidant and hydroxylated species of catalyst in a slow step. This complex reacts with substrate in subsequent fast steps to give the products. No spectral evidence was obtained for such a complex, since no appreciable change in the absorption spectra of oxidant and catalyst in the presence of each other was observed. A feeble interaction is probably involved. However, a kinetic evidence for the complex formation is obtained. Such type of complex formation between catalyst and oxidant has been reported earlier¹⁹. Osmium(VIII) and Mn^{VII} are known to form complex with other species in view of their vacant d-orbitals.

Scheme 3 leads to the following rate law

$$\frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{T}}} = k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k K [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}}}{1 + K [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}}} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= -\frac{[\text{MnO}_4^-]}{dt} \\ &= \frac{k K [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}} [\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{T}}}{(1 + K [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}}) (1 + K [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}})} \quad (5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{T}}} = k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k K [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}}}{1 + K [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}}} \quad (6)$$

Eq. (6) may be rearranged to the form (7) which is suitable for verification.

$$\frac{[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}}}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{k K [\text{OH}^-]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (7)$$

According to eq. (7) the plot of $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}}/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}}$ is expected to be linear which is verified. The

both favorable for electron transfer processes. The positive value of ΔS^\ddagger indicates the complex is highly ordered than the reactants a molecule which supports the proposed mechanism. The favorable enthalpy was due to release of energy on solution changes in the transition state. The values of ΔS^\ddagger within the range of radical reaction have been ascribed²¹ (Table 2) to the nature of electron pairing and unpairing processes, and to the loss of degree of freedom, formerly available to the reaction on the formation of rigid transition state.

The uncatalysed reaction²² exhibit unit order $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$

Table 1. Effect of variation of $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$, $[\text{GH}]$, $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ and $[\text{OH}^-]$ on the osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of guanidine hydrochloride by permanganate in aqueous alkaline medium

Temp. = 27°, I = 2.00 mol dm ⁻³					
$[\text{MnO}_4^-] \times 10^4$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{GH}] \times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] \times 10^6$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{OH}^-]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$k_{\text{obs}} 10^3$ (s ⁻¹)	
				Expt.	Calcd.*
0.5	2.0	3.0	1.0	2.14	2.26
1.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	2.00	2.26
2.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	1.95	2.26
3.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	2.16	2.26
5.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	2.21	2.26
2.0	0.5	3.0	1.0	2.02	-
2.0	1.0	3.0	1.0	2.00	-
2.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	2.05	-
2.0	3.0	3.0	1.0	1.96	-
2.0	5.0	3.0	1.0	2.21	-
2.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	0.40	0.39
2.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	0.78	0.80
2.0	2.0	5.0	1.0	1.46	1.50
2.0	2.0	8.0	1.0	2.14	2.24
2.0	2.0	10.0	1.0	4.08	3.90
2.0	2.0	3.0	0.2	0.80	0.81
2.0	2.0	3.0	0.6	1.78	1.73
2.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	2.14	2.28
2.0	2.0	3.0	1.4	2.41	2.57
2.0	2.0	3.0	2.0	2.93	2.87

slope and intercept of such plot lead to the values of k and K as $1.29 \times 10^2 \pm 9.50 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $28.5 \pm 1.4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. These constants are used to calculate the rate constants over different experimental conditions. There is a good agreement between calculated and observed rate constants (Table 1). The values of K obtained are in agreement with earlier reports²⁰.

The negligible effect of ionic strength and solvent polarity qualitatively explains the involvement of neutral species in the reaction. The values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were

Table 2. Activation parameters for the osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of guanidine hydrochloride by permanganate in aqueous alkaline medium with respect to slow step of the Scheme 3

Activation parameter	Values	
	Uncatalysed	Catalysed
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	48 ± 2	52 ± 2
log A	17.2 ± 3	20 ± 2
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	43 ± 2	60 ± 3
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	34.1 ± 1.6	46 ± 3
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-32.3 ± 6	15 ± 1

and less than unit order each in $[\text{GH}]$ and $[\text{OH}^-]$. Addition of products has no significant effect on the reaction rate, but increasing ionic strength and decreasing dielectric constant of the medium increases the rate. The oxidation process has been shown to proceed with the formation of complex between guanidine hydrochloride and MnO_4^- . The rate determining step is the decomposition of complex. However, in the present catalysed reaction we have noticed entirely different observation such as unit order in $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ and $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ and less than unit order in $[\text{OH}^-]$ which zero order dependence in $[\text{GH}]$. There is no effect of ionic strength and solvent polarity. The reaction proceeds via the formation of a complex between oxidant and hydroxylated species of catalyst.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade chemicals. Doubly distilled water was used throughout this work. The stock solution of potassium permanganate (B.D.H.) was prepared and standardized against oxalic acid²³. Potassium manganate solution was prepared as described by Carrington and Symons²⁴ as follows : an aqueous solution of potassium permanganate was heated to boiling $> 120^\circ\text{C}$ in 8.0 mol dm^{-3} KOH solution until it turned green. The solid potassium manganate, which formed on cooling, was recrystallised from the KOH solution. Using the required amount of recrystallised sample, a stock solution of potassium manganate was then prepared in aqueous KOH. The solution was standardised by measuring the absorbance on a Hitachi 150-20 spectrophotometer with a 1 cm quartz cell at 608 nm ($\epsilon = 1530 \pm 20 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The stock solution of guanidine hydrochloride (s.d fine) was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of sample in doubly distilled water. The osmium(VIII) solution was made by dissolving OsO_4 (Johnson-Mathey) in 0.50 mol dm^{-3} sodium hydroxide solution and its concentration was ascertained by addition of excess of potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) solution followed by titration of unreacted ferrocyanide with standard cerium(IV) solution in acid medium. Sodium perchlorate was used to maintain a constant ionic strength and NaOH is used to get the required alkalinity.

Kinetic procedure : All the kinetic measurements were performed under pseudo-first conditions at $27 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ unless stated otherwise. The reaction was initiated by mix-

Fig. 1. Verification of rate law (6) in the form of (7) for the osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of guanidine hydrochloride by alkaline permanganate (conditions as in Table 1).

ing previously thermo stated solutions of MnO_4^- and guanidine hydrochloride which also contained the required amount of osmium(VIII) catalyst, NaOH and NaClO_4 to maintain the required alkalinity and ionic strength respectively. The progress of the reaction was followed by measuring decrease in absorbance of permanganate at 526 nm as a function of time. Earlier it was verified that there is negligible interference from other reagents at this wavelength. The application of Beer's law to permanganate at 526 nm had been verified giving $\epsilon = 2083 \pm 50 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Literature $\epsilon = 2200 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)¹⁰.

The first order rate constants were obtained from the slopes of $\log [\text{MnO}_4^-]$ versus time plots in almost all the cases the plots were linear up to 80% completion of the reaction and (k_{obs}) were reproducible within $\pm 5\%$. During the course of measurements, the solution changed from violet to blue and then to green. The spectrum of the green solution was identified to that of MnO_4^{2-} . It is probable that the blue colour originates from violet of permanganate and the green from the manganate, excluding the accumulation of hypomanganate. It is also evident from Fig. 2 that the concentration of permanganate decreases at 520 nm whereas the concentration of manganate increases at 608 nm.

Fig. 2. Spectral changes during for the osmium(VIII) catalysed permanganate oxidation of guanidine hydrochloride in aqueous alkaline medium at 27 °C. Scanning time interval = 2 min. $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{GH}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{OH}^-] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] = 3.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $l = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

The effect of dissolved oxygen on the rate of the reaction was checked by preparing the reaction mixture and following the reaction in a nitrogen atmosphere. There are no significant changes in the results obtained in the presence of nitrogen and in the presence of air. In view of the ubiquitous contamination of carbonate in basic solutions, the effect of carbonate on the reaction was studied. Added carbonate showed no effect on the reaction rate. However, fresh solutions were used while conducting the experiments.

In view of modest concentration of alkali used in reaction medium, attention was also given to the effect of the surface of the reaction vessel on the kinetics. The use of polythene or acrylic ware and quartz or polyacrylates

cells gave the same results, indicating that the surfaces does not have any significant effect on the rate.

Further a minute quantity ($10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) of osmium(VIII) is sufficient to catalyse the reaction. The active species of osmium(VIII) is found to be $[\text{OsO}_5(\text{OH})_3]^{3-}$. The overall mechanistic sequence described here is constituent with product studies, mechanistic studies and kinetic studies.

The oxidant species, MnO_4^- required the $\text{pH} > 12$ and below which the system gets disturbed due to the formation of colloidal solution by the reductant and the reaction will proceed further to give reduced product of oxidant as Mn^{IV} , which develops yellow turbidity slowly. Thus it becomes apparent that in carrying out this reac-

Fig. 3. First order plots in $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ on the osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of guanidine hydrochloride by permanganate in aqueous alkaline at 27 °C. $[\text{MnO}_4^-] \times 10^4 =$ (1) 0.5, (2) 1.0, (3) 2.0, (4) 3.0, (5) 5.0 mol dm^{-3} (conditions as in Table 1).

tion the role of pH in the reaction media is crucial. It is also noteworthy that under the conditions studied, the reaction occurs in two successive one-electron (Scheme 1) rather than two-electron reduction in a single step.

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Appendices

Scheme 3 leads to the rate law

$$\frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{T}}} = k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k K [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}}}{1 + K [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}}} \quad (4)$$

The above rate law can be derived as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= k [\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{f}} [\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})_2^-] \\ &= k K [\text{OsO}_3(\text{OH})_3^-]_{\text{f}} [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{f}} [\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{f}} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$[\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{T}} = [\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{f}} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}} &= [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{f}} + [\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})_2^-] \\ &= [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{f}} + K [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{f}} [\text{OH}^-] \\ &= [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{f}} (1 + K [\text{OH}^-]) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

and

$$[\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}} = [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{f}} + [\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})_2^-]$$

$$= [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{f}} + K [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{f}} [\text{OH}^-]$$

$$= [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{f}} (1 + K [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{f}})$$

$$[\text{OH}^-]_{\text{f}} = [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}} / (1 + K [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{f}}) \quad (8)$$

Substituting the values of eqs. (6), (7) and (8) into eq. (5) we get

$$\text{Rate} = - \frac{[\text{MnO}_4^-]}{dt} = \frac{k K [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}} [\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{T}}}{(1 + K [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}}) (1 + K [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}})} \quad (9)$$

In view of low concentration of Os^{VIII} used, the term $(1 + K [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}})$ in the denominator of eq. (9) is approximated to unity. Thus, eq. (9) becomes eq. (10).

$$\frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{T}}} = k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k K [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}}}{1 + K [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}}} \quad (10)$$

Eq. (10) may be rearranged to the form (11) which is suitable for verification.

$$\frac{[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}}}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{k K [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}}} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (11)$$

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